

CardinalFit: A Shiny App. to Fit Cardinal Models

User's Guide

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About CardinalFit

Predictive Microbiology deals with the development of accurate and versatile mathematical models, able to describe the evolution of microorganisms in food products as a function of environmental conditions, which are assumed to be measurable. Although there are a few classification schemes of predictive microbiology models, they have been traditionally classified into primary and secondary models.

CardinalFit is a Shiny application designed to fit *cardinal parameter models*, which are secondary models that describe the growth rate of microorganisms as a function of extrinsic and/or intrinsic factors. These are models that estimate the optimum growth rate, and the minimum, optimum and maximum values of extrinsic and intrinsic factors (e.g. temperature, pH, water activity) that characterise the growth of a given microbial strain.

CardinalFit is intended to be fed with data from challenge studies, this is, studies on growth of a microorganism artificially inoculated in broth.

The Cardinal Parameter Model

The general cardinal parameter model used to describe and predict the effect of different environmental factors on the growth rate of a microorganism is based on a modular approach called the "gamma concept" (Zwietering et al., 1992), described as,

$$\mu_{max} = \mu_{opt} \cdot \gamma(T) \cdot \gamma(pH) \cdot \gamma(aw) \cdot \gamma(inh)$$

where:

μ_{max} : maximum growth rate (h^{-1} or day^{-1}) of the studied bacterial strain

μ_{opt} : optimum growth rate (h^{-1} or day^{-1}) of the studied bacterial strain

$\gamma(T)$, $\gamma(pH)$, $\gamma(aw)$, $\gamma(inh)$: dimensionless functions describing the relative effects of temperature (T), pH, water activity (aw) and different measurable inhibitors (inh) like undissociated organic acids or CO_2 . The functions $\gamma(T)$, $\gamma(pH)$, $\gamma(aw)$, $\gamma(inh)$ have a range between 0 and 1, $\gamma=0$ when growth is fully inhibited and $\gamma=1$ when growth is not inhibited at all by the factor.

Cardinal Parameters

Many γ -type functions have been proposed for temperature, pH, aw and lactic acid. CardinalFit adjusts the cardinal parameter model using the general equation for γ , proposed by Rosso et al. (1995),

$\gamma(X)_n$

$$= \begin{cases} 0, & X \leq X_{\min} \\ \frac{(X - X_{\max}) \cdot (X - X_{\min})^n}{(X_{\text{opt}} - X_{\min})^{n-1} \cdot \left[\frac{(X_{\text{opt}} - X_{\min}) \cdot (X - X_{\text{opt}}) - (X_{\text{opt}} - X_{\max}) \cdot (X_{\text{opt}} + X_{\min} - n \cdot X)}{(n-1) \cdot X_{\text{opt}} + X_{\min} - n \cdot X} \right]}, & X_{\min} < X < X_{\max} \\ 0, & X \geq X_{\max} \end{cases}$$

X : intrinsic or extrinsic factor under study; temperature, pH or aw

X_{\min} : value of the factor below which no growth occurs

X_{\max} : value of the factor above which no growth occurs

X_{opt} : value at which bacterial growth is optimum

n : shape parameter ($n = 2$ for temperature and water activity; and $n = 1$ for pH).

X_{\min} , X_{\max} and X_{opt} are known as cardinal parameters, and are estimated by fitting the cardinal parameter model to growth data from experiments carried out in broth.

More precisely, T_{\min} , T_{\max} and T_{opt} are determined from $\gamma(T)$; pH_{\min} , pH_{\max} and pH_{opt} are determined from $\gamma(pH)$; and aw_{\min} , aw_{\max} and aw_{opt} are determined from $\gamma(aw)$. Often, when adjusting the cardinal parameter model for aw, aw_{\max} is set to one, because it is in effect the maximum value of the water activity measurement.

Cardinal Parameter Models (CPM) available in CardinalFit

CPM for temperature

CardinalFit adjusts the Cardinal Temperature Model with Inflection (CTMI) (Rosso et al., 1993) to determine optimum growth rate (μ_{opt}) and the cardinal parameters T_{\min} , T_{\max} and T_{opt} .

$$\sqrt{\mu_{\max}} = \sqrt{\mu_{\text{opt}} \cdot \gamma(T)} + \varepsilon$$

$$\gamma(T) = \begin{cases} 0, & T \leq T_{\min} \\ \frac{(T - T_{\max}) \cdot (T - T_{\min})^2}{(T_{\text{opt}} - T_{\min}) \cdot \left[\frac{(T_{\text{opt}} - T_{\min}) \cdot (T - T_{\text{opt}}) - (T_{\text{opt}} - T_{\max}) \cdot (T_{\text{opt}} + T_{\min} - 2T)}{(T_{\text{opt}} + T_{\min} - 2T)} \right]}, & T_{\min} < T < T_{\max} \\ 0, & T \geq T_{\max} \end{cases}$$

To fit this model to the growth data, the response variable, maximum growth rate (μ_{max}), is square-root transformed to reduce heterocedasticity. The residuals are represented by ε , and are assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean zero and variance σ^2 .

CPM for pH

To determine optimum growth rate (μ_{opt}) and the cardinal parameters pH_{min} , pH_{max} and pH_{opt} , CardinalFit adjusts the cardinal model for pH proposed by Le Marc et al. (2002).

$$\sqrt{\mu_{max}} = \sqrt{\mu_{opt} \cdot \gamma(pH)} + \varepsilon$$

$$\gamma(pH) = \begin{cases} 0, & pH \leq pH_{min} \\ \frac{(pH - pH_{max}) \cdot (pH - pH_{min})}{[(pH_{opt} - pH_{min}) \cdot (pH - pH_{opt}) - (pH_{opt} - pH_{max}) \cdot (pH_{min} - pH)]}, & pH_{min} < pH < pH_{max} \\ 0, & pH \geq pH_{max} \end{cases}$$

To fit this model to the growth data, the response variable, maximum growth rate (μ_{max}), is square-root transformed to reduce heterocedasticity. The residuals are represented by ε , and are assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean zero and variance σ^2 .

CPM for aw

CardinalFit adjusts the cardinal model for water activity from Rosso et al. (1993) to extract optimum growth rate (μ_{opt}) and the cardinal parameters aw_{min} and aw_{opt} .

$$\sqrt{\mu_{max}} = \sqrt{\mu_{opt} \cdot \gamma(aw)} + \varepsilon$$

$$\gamma(aw) = \begin{cases} 0, & aw \leq aw_{min} \\ \frac{(aw - 1.0) \cdot (aw - aw_{min})^2}{(aw_{opt} - aw_{min}) \cdot \left[\frac{(aw_{opt} - aw_{min}) \cdot (aw - aw_{opt}) - (aw_{opt} - 1.0)}{(aw_{opt} + aw_{min} - 2aw)} \right]}, & aw_{min} < aw < 1.0 \\ 0, & aw \geq 1.0 \end{cases}$$

To fit this model to the growth data, the response variable, maximum growth rate (μ_{max}), is square-root transformed to reduce heterocedasticity. The residuals are represented by ε , and are assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean zero and variance σ^2 .

CPM for inhibitory substance

For the inhibitors (inh) including undissociated organic acids, CO₂ and others, the cardinal parameter model proposed by Le Marc et al. (2002) and Coroller et al. (2005) is adjusted by the CardinalFit app.

$$\sqrt{\mu_{max}} = \sqrt{\mu_{opt} \cdot \gamma(inh)} + \varepsilon$$

$$\gamma(inh) = 1 - \left(\frac{inh}{MIC}\right)^\alpha$$

Inh: concentration of the inhibiting substance or compound (e.g. undissociated organic acid (mM), CO₂ (%))

MIC: Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (mM or %, accordingly)

α: shape parameter of the curve (α = 1 the shape is linear; α > 1 the shape is downward concave; and α < 1 the shape is upward concave)

To fit this model to the growth data, the response variable, maximum growth rate (μ_{max}), is square-root transformed to reduce heterocedasticity. The residuals are represented by ε , and are assumed to follow a normal distribution with mean zero and variance σ^2 . The model parameters are MIC and α .

How to Use CardinalFit

Under the gamma concept, the different intrinsic and extrinsic factors have separate effects on the maximum growth rate, which implies that the cardinal values associated to a factor can be also estimated separately. CardinalFit performs this task and is intuitive and user-friendly.

Go to: <https://ubarron.shinyapps.io/CardinalFit/>

Step 1: Save dataset in .csv

The data must be saved in .csv file, ensuring that it contains the model inputs in two different columns:

- *Factor*: values of the intrinsic or extrinsic factor (i.e., temperature, pH, aw or the concentration of the inhibitory substance)
- μ_{max} : maximum growth rate of the microorganism estimated at the corresponding value of the intrinsic/extrinsic factor

Step 2: Load dataset and select CPM

- Click on the navigator bar **Dataset & Initial Values**
- Upload the dataset using the **Browse** button, then select the character ([;], [,] or [:]) that separates the columns. Click on **Load dataset**.
- Select the cardinal parameter model to fit from the dropdown menu “Select Cardinal Model”
 - CMTI stands for cardinal model for temperature with inflection
 - CMPH stands for cardinal model for pH
 - CMAW stands for cardinal model for aw
 - CINH stands for cardinal model for inhibitory substance
- Select the “X Variable” and the “Y Variable” from the dropdown menus. Example: “X Variable”=Temp (for temperature) and “Y Variable”=GR (for maximum growth rate in h⁻¹).

- A scatterplot of the data will appear on the right-hand side box, as well as a simulation curve driven by the initial values given to the model

Step 3: Approximate initial values

- Provide sensible initial values for the model parameters on the left-hand side input box, observing that the simulation curve must lie close to the observations.
- Click on the **Run model** button.

In this screenshot, the values provided to **Tmax**, **Tmin**, **MUopt** and **Topt** were 45, -1.5, 1.2 and 36. These initial values enabled a close description of the observations.

Step 4: Fit and assess the model

- Click on the navigator bar **Fitting Results**. Beware that for large datasets, model fitting may take longer.
- Once the model has adjusted, in the left column box "Fitting", you will get four sets of results:
 - Parameter estimates containing mean values, standard errors, t values and probability $Pr(>|t|)$
 - Coefficient of variation in % of the parameters computed as the standard error divided by the mean value.
 - Correlation matrix of the parameters
 - Goodness-of-fit parameters such as residual standard error, log-likelihood, Akaike information criterion and Bayesian information criterion.
- On the right-hand side box, you will find a series of display tabs
 - The tab "Fitted model" shows the graph of the fitted model and the 95% confidence interval.

- The tab “Fitted versus observed” shows the fitted versus observed values in the square root transformation scale (as the model was fitted)
- The tab “Residuals versus fitted” shows the residuals versus fitted values in the square root transformation scale (as the model was fitted)
- All of the above graphs can be saved as PNG files.

Step 5: Predict μ_{max}

The last tab of the right-hand side box “Prediction” enables the user to obtain a fitted or predicted value of the maximum growth rate μ_{max} , at a given value of the intrinsic/extrinsic factor.

Once the value of temperature, pH, aw or concentration of the inhibitory compound is entered (independent variable), the model returns the following calculations:

- The fitted response variable as the square root transformed $\sqrt{\mu_{max}}$ as well as its associated standard error, $SE(\sqrt{\mu_{max}})$
- The mean μ_{max} in the original scale (back-transformed)
- The 95% confidence interval for the mean μ_{max} (interval in which the true value of the mean μ_{max} lies)

- The 95% prediction interval for μ_{max} (interval in which the individual value of μ_{max} lies, which accounts for both the uncertainty in estimating the population mean plus the random variation of the individual values.

How to Cite CardinalFit

Cadavez, V. and Gonzales-Barron, U. (2020) CardinalFit: A Shiny App. to Fit Cardinal Models. <https://ubarron.shinyapps.io/CardinalFit/>

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